

Tiantai

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Entry tags: Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Tiantai school (tiantai zong 天台宗), Religious Group, Chinese Religion

Tiantai was the first Buddhist school founded in China. Though it traced its origin to the Indian philosopher-saint Nagarjuna and ultimately to the Shakyamuni Buddha himself, its intellectual character was shaped by Zhiyi (538–97), a Chinese monk. Zhiyi made two sojourns to Mount Tiantai, a mountain in southeastern China, and asked in his will that the Sui Prince Yang Guang build a monastery there. The school was subsequently named after the mountain, which literally means “platform of the sky.” The Tiantai School was not formed by the time Zhiyi died, but Guanding (561–632), one of his disciples, constructed a Tiantai lineage by connecting Zhiyi to the historical Buddha, an Indian figure who had lived centuries earlier. This is considered by modern scholars “a watershed in the history of religious ideas” in that it constitutes a defining element in the development of group identity and sectarian consciousness within Chinese Buddhism. The intellectual foundations of Tiantai took shape in a period when a long-divided China was transformed into a unified state. Zhiyi, originally from an elite family in the south, integrated Buddhism as philosophy popular among southern elites at the time, with meditation techniques that he inherited from his teacher Huisi (514–577), a northerner. As a result, Tiantai is characterized by a strong philosophical content and at the same time an emphasis on meditative practice; these are considered the two wings of a bird. Tiantai was deeply influenced by the Madhyamaka philosophy of Indian Buddhism and developed the Madhyamaka idea of Two Truths (i.e. the absolute truth and the conventional truth) into Three Truths (or the Threefold Truth): 1) all things are empty in the sense that they are produced through causes and conditions and therefore have no self-nature; 2) they do have tentative or provisional existence; 3) being both empty and provisional is the nature of everything, which is the Truth of the Mean. Tiantai believes that all beings can be divided into ten realms – the hell dwellers, hungry ghosts, animals, human beings, demigods, heavenly gods, voice hearers, pratyeka-buddhas, bodhisattvas, and buddhas. In Tiantai thought, these are so interwoven and interpenetrated that they are “immanent in a single instant of thought.” In other words, in every thought-moment, all possible worlds are involved. For the same reason, after a doctrinal debate within Tiantai in the 10th – 11th century, the idea of “inherent evil in nature” or “inherent inclusion” became orthodox. It is believed that human nature, as well as the nature of all beings, contains the nature of beings of other nine realms, which is to say, humans, buddhas, hell dwellers and so forth all have both good and evil in their nature. This idea distinguishes Tiantai not only from other schools of Chinese Buddhism, which consider the Buddha Nature purely enlightened and good, but also from mainstream Confucianism, which believes that all humans are born with a purely good nature. This feature attracted supporters to Tiantai in the late imperial era (16th - 19th centuries), who tended to challenge Confucian ideology. Like other schools in Chinese Buddhism, Tiantai as a religious group is not congregational and thus its organization has remained loose and its identity fluid. Except for about a dozen of eminent monks historically recognized as patriarchs in the Tiantai lineage, most monastics and lay Buddhists do not strongly identify themselves with any particular school and usually study under masters specializing in various schools. For this reason, Tiantai had been studied by modern scholars mainly as school of philosophy and doctrines. But this approach, equating Tiantai Buddhism simply with its philosophy, tends to eclipse the significance of Tiantai’s social network, its contributions to Buddhist rituals and communal life, and other important aspects that more and more scholars have been taking on in their research on Tiantai.

Date Range: 538 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Jiangnan

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China, Jiangnan

In the Tang Dynasty, in addition to Mount Tiantai in the Jiangnan area, Yuquan Monastery in Hubei, which is a major Tiantai institution originally founded by Zhiyi, and the capital Chang'an and its surrounding environs including Mount Wutai to the north are two other long-standing and vital centers of Tiantai learning. The northern centers may have been more syncretic. After the Huichang persecution (842-6), the effort to reconstitute Tiantai teaching a century later brought Zhanran (711-782), who based himself on Mt. Tiantai, and his works to the fore. Since then, Mt. Tiantai and its nearby cities such as Ningbo became the center of Tiantai Buddhism. In the Tiantai history composed in the 12th and 13th century, the northern centers were neglected. It is not until the first half of the 20th century that Tanxu (1875-1962), after came to Ningbo from the north to study Tiantai, spread Tiantai to Manchuria and then Hong Kong. His disciples further brought the tradition to many places in the world. Tiantai was transmitted to Japan in the 8-9th century and to Korea in the 11th century. The transmission is not one-way. In the middle of the tenth century, when Tiantai texts were destroyed in uprisings, many of them were brought back to China by Japanese monks and Chinese merchants. The Cheontae sagyo ui 天台四教儀 by Goryeo monk Chegwan 諦觀 was very influential in China. However, over the centuries, both Tendai in Japan and Cheontae in Korea have gained their unique characters that are different from the Chinese Tiantai. For this reason, they are not discussed in depth in this entry.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Swanson, Paul L (translation and commentary). 2018. *Clear Serenity, Quiet Insight: T'ien-t'ai Chih-i's Mo-ho chih-kuan*, Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press.
- Source 2: Hurvitz, Leon, 1963, *Chih-i (538–599): An Introduction to the Life and Ideas of a Chinese Buddhist Monk*, Bruxelles: Inst. Belge des Hautes Etudes Chinoises.

Notes: Scholarship on Chih-i (Zhiyi 智顛), the founder of Tiantai, is extensive. *Clear Serenity, Quiet Insight* is an annotated, full translation of his most important work *Mo-ho chih-kuan* (Mohe zhiguan 摩訶止觀).

– Source 1: Mou Zongsan, "The Place of Tiantai Tradition in Chinese Buddhism" (天台宗在中國佛教中的地位) trans. Jason Clower, in Clower, Jason. *Late Works of Mou Zongsan : Selected Essays on Chinese Philosophy*, BRILL, 2014.

– Source 2: Clower, Jason, 2010, *The Unlikely Buddhologist: Tiantai Buddhism in Mou Zongsan's New Confucianism*, Leiden [etc.]: Brill.

Notes: This translated essay by Mou Zongsan (牟宗三, 1909-1995) and the monograph on Mou's Tiantai Buddhism showcase how the Tiantai tradition has been serving as an intellectual and spiritual resource in modern and contemporary Chinese culture.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1909 CE - 1995 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

– Source 1: Jülch, Thomas. 2019. *Zhipan's Account of the History of Buddhism in China, Volume 1, Fozu tongji, juan 34-38 : from the Times of the Buddha to the Nanbeichao Era*. Leiden: Brill.

Notes: A partial translation of *Fozu tongji* (佛祖統記), a 13th century Buddhist historiography from the perspective of the Tiantai orthodoxy.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://en.chamshantemple.org/messages/aboutus/index.php?channelId=8§ionId=109&itemId=87&attachId=0&langCd=EN>

– Source 1 Description: Cham Shan Temple in Canada, founded by disciples of Tanxu, is a monastery of Tiantai Buddhism.

– Source 1 URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/buddhism-tiantai/>

– Source 1 Description: Ziporyn, Brook, "Tiantai Buddhism", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2020 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.). A summary of the Tiantai philosophy developed from the sixth to eleventh centuries.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.rep.routledge.com/articles/overview/buddhist-philosophy-chinese/v-1/sections/the-chinese-buddhist-schools-tiantai>

– Source 2 Description: Lusthaus, Dan. *The Chinese Buddhist Schools: Tiantai*. *Buddhist philosophy, Chinese*, 1998, doi:10.4324/9780415249126-G002-1. Routledge Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Taylor and Francis,

Notes: Notice that both sources were written by scholars of Buddhist philosophy, which may give readers a bias that Tiantai is purely a philosophical tradition. However, Tiantai has been rich in rituals, meditative and devotional methods, which should not be neglected due to the lack of online sources in English.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.acmuller.net/kor-bud/sagyoui.html>

– Source 1 Description: Outline of the Tiantai Fourfold Teachings 天台四教儀 Compiled by the Goryeo Śramaṇa Chegwan 高麗沙門諦觀, Translated by A. Charles Muller

– Source 2 URL: <https://bookgb.bfn.org/article/0234.htm>

– Source 2 Description: A memoir of Tanxu (倭虛 1875-1963), who promulgated Tiantai in Northern China and Hong Kong. For a study of this monk, see Carter, J. H. (2014). *Heart of Buddha, Heart of China: The Life of Tanxu, a Twentieth Century Monk*.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: 1. Other Buddhist schools: 1-A. The Sanlun School: According to Jinhua Chen's research, when Guanding 灌頂 (561-632) compiled Zhiyi's 智顓 (538-597) Lotus lectures, he borrowed a lot of passages and ideas from Jizang's 吉藏 (549-623) Lotus Commentaries, and Tiantai monks after Guanding took great pains to cover up this "plagiarism." They asserted Tiantai's superiority over other Buddhist traditions in China, especially the Sanlun School that Jizang founded. They promoted the theory that Jizang was disciple to Guanding (see Guanding's biography in Xu gaoseng zhuan 續高僧傳). Later, to make this position more historically plausible, Tiantai adherents turned to picturing Jizang as Zhiyi's disciple and fabricated three letters in Jizang's name to Zhiyi as evidence (see no. 102 in Guoqing bailu 國清百錄). Zhanran 湛然 (711-782, the sixth Tiantai patriarch) attempted to explain away Jizang and Zhiyi's differences in the classification of doctrines (判教). His disciples further forged Tiantai's fame in Japan and India. For example there is the story of Zhanran meeting with Hanguang 含光 (n.d.), who told Zhanran about the fame of Tiantai in India where he had travelled in the 740s with his teacher Amoghavajra (706-74) (see Hanguang's biography in Song gaoseng zhuan 宋高僧傳). They also fabricated two more documents to show Sanlun's subordination to Tiantai, both included in Guoqing bailu (no.103 and 100). 1-B. The Chan School: According to Brook Ziporyn, after the death of Zhanran, especially after the persecution of Buddhism in 845, Tiantai found itself in crisis, while Chan was showing an outstanding capacity for synthesizing ideas from other Buddhist schools. Qingliang Chengguan 清涼澄觀 (738-839), the fourth Huayan patriarch, studied under Zhanran and incorporated in his work elements of both Chan and Tiantai, including the notion of inherent evil in the Buddha nature. Yet Chengguan's student, Guifeng Zongmi 圭峰宗密 (780-841), eliminated the Tiantai influence while absorbing ideas from Chan and Huayan. Deshao 德韶 (881-972), renowned in his time as a reviver of Tiantai, was closely associated with the Fayen branch of Chan, and his student, Yongming Yanshou 永明延壽 (954-974), influenced by Zongmi, attempted to unify Tiantai, Huayan, and Yogacara teachings under a form of Chan, emphasizing the "one pure formless mind." Against this background, Tiantai ideas and practices "appeared quaint and cumbersome." Zongmi's version of Chan doctrine became the most common target of Tiantai authors such as Zhili 知禮 (960-1028). Ziporyn summarizes Zhili and his followers' criticisms against Chan into four points, all of which were echoed by Tiantai polemicists of later periods in China: 1) The excessive emphasis on meditation at the expense of doctrine was allegedly advocated by many Chan masters, whereas Tiantai claims to value doctrine and meditation equally. 2) Chan allegedly rejects words, whereas Tiantai sees words as a *necessary* vehicle to enlightenment (Ziporyn considers this a "fundamental misunderstanding" of Zhiyi's original idea regarding the skillful means for enlightenment). 3) The "Home Mountain" (shanjia) people of Tiantai, as represented by Zhili, would defeat their "Off Mountain" (shanwai) rivals and become the orthodox proponents of Tiantai. The Home Mountain faction criticized Zongmi's version of Chan doctrine, which influenced Off Mountain thinkers. For Zongmi, every phenomenon is ultimate reality modified under various conditions, just as waves of different shapes are ultimately water. For the

Home Mountain Tiantai, however, every phenomenon is ultimate reality that itself contains all possibilities and distinctions. For this reason, in Chan the mind is essentially pure, but for the Home Mountain Tiantai, mind is on equal footing with any other given phenomenon. 4) The Chan lineage claimed a special authority deriving directly from Sakyamuni himself and represented a special transmission of the buddha-mind outside that recorded in the sutras. The Tiantai polemicists consider this claim historically unfounded and religiously misguided. 2. Indigenous Chinese religions: In a manual of the Bodhisattva Ordination Rite attributed to the Tiantai patriarch Huisi 慧思 (515-577) but in fact more likely composed in the late Tang, indigenous Chinese deities are invoked after a list of Buddhas, bodhisattvas, and Indian protective deities in Tiantai manuals. Ciyun Zunshi (964-1032), throughout his forty-year career as a Tiantai master, campaigned actively against the “depraved” local custom of offering blood sacrifice to ancestors and gods. The Tiantaishan Fangwai zhi 天台山方外志, a gazetteer composed in the early 17th century for Mt. Tiantai, shows that collections of Buddhist, Daoist, and Confucianist books were all held in the monastery libraries on Mt. Tiantai. In general, many literati who supported Tiantai practiced Daoism and were Confucian scholars at the same time. 3. Catholicism: Youxi Chuandeng 幽溪傳燈 (1554-1628), one of the leading Tiantai monks of the early 17th century, exchanged poems with Yang Tingyun 楊廷筠 (1562-1627), the scholar-official who had converted to Catholicism. Yang helped Youxi’s monastery exempt from taxation.

Reference: Daniel Stevenson. *Protocols of Power: Tz'u-yun Tsun-shih (964-1032) and T'ien-t'ai Lay Buddhist Ritual in the Sung*. (Peter Gregory, Daniel Getz), *Buddhism in the Sung*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press.

Reference: Jinhua Chen. *Making and Remaking History: A Study of Tiantai Sectarian Historiography*. Tokyo: The International Institute for Buddhist Studies.

Reference: N. Standaert. *Yang Tingyun, Confucian and Christian in Late Ming China*. Brill.

Reference: Daniel Getz undefined. *Popular Religion and Pure Land in Song Dynasty Tiantai Bodhisattva Precept Ordination Ceremonies*. (William Bodiford), *Going Forth: Visions of Buddhist Vinaya*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press.

Reference: Brook Ziporyn. *Anti-Chan Polemics in Post Tang Tiantai*. *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies*, 17(1)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 1840 CE

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Tiantai authors often commented critically on some practices of Chan. Most of the Tiantai patriarchs and authors accepted Chan as a legitimate Buddhist approach (Zhili classified Chan one of the “special teachings,” biejiao 別教), but rejected the claim that Chan surpasses Tiantai’s perfect, “round teaching” (yuanjiao 圓教) and condemned some Chan rhetoric such as that scriptures are useless for enlightenment.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 1840 CE

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Rongdao Lai points out that there were three forms of affiliation based on religious kinship in Chinese Buddhism: tonsure, Dharma, and ordination. A monk or nun was usually tonsured in a small, local temple, through which they became novices. While every novice was expected to take full ordination after a probationary period, only a select few were granted Dharma transmission. Since the Ming and Qing, whereas a large majority of monks and nuns belonged to the Chan lineages of Linji or Caodong upon tonsure, Tiantai and Huayan lineages were bestowed during Dharma transmission. In Chinese Buddhism, it was not uncommon for a monk to receive transmissions in more than one lineage through tonsure, ordination, or/and Dharma transmission. In the late imperial period, Dharma lineages were often associated with monastic leadership, prescribing the order of the succession to the abbotship of a certain monastery. Yet, Lai argues that Tanxu 倓虛 (1875-1962), an eminent Tiantai monk of the twentieth century, intentionally separated Dharma transmission from the management of the monastic community. He bestowed Dharma transmission of the Tiantai lineage to as many as he deemed appropriate and urged them to travel far and wide to spread the Dharma and the Tiantai tradition. For lay Buddhists, whether and to what degree they are affiliated with Tiantai depend on personal preference. One may take a Tiantai monk as his spiritual mentor but also have similar relationships with monks of other schools at the same time. Gong Zizhen 龔自珍 (1792-1841), a prominent poet of the 19th century, claimed himself to be a Tiantai Buddhist without receiving any recognition from the Tiantai monastic community.

Reference: Lang Chen. Mad but not Chan: Tu Long (1543-1605) and Tiantai Buddhism. *Fo Guang Journal of Buddhist Studies*, 5(2)

Reference: Rongdao Lai. Tiantai Transnationalism: Mobility, Identity, and Lineage Networks in Modern Chinese Buddhism. (Philip Clart, Adam Jones), *Transnational Religious Spaces*. Berlin/Boston: De Gruyter.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: According to Getz, in the late Tang and Northern Song, a number of elements not found in earlier Tiantai ceremonies were introduced to address in a more focused way the needs and concerns of the lay audience. This change may have been partly caused by monastics learning the consequences of losing touch with society, that is, persecution and criticism. Tiantai monks and

supporters also promoted Tiantai by writing and lecturing. However, their recruits might also support other religious groups at the same time. Using the word "member" in the context of Chinese Buddhism must be done with caution.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 1840 CE

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:
– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:
– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:
– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:
– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:
– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Tiantai was supported by royal courts at certain points in Chinese history, often when political figures supported Buddhism in general. Zhiyi, its intellectual founder, was supported by the courts of the Chen and Sui. Emperor Wen (r. 581 -604) of the Sui dynasty persisted in his patronage of Zhiyi and his group, partly in an effort to placate the southern elite. Zhiyi was particularly close to Prince Yang Guang, who after Zhiyi's death ascended the throne to become Emperor Yang (r. 604-618) of the Sui. Zhiyi administered the bodhisattva ordination for him, gave him the clerical name "Zongchi" (總持), and the prince gave him the honorary title "Zhizhe" (智者). Shortly before he died, Zhiyi asked for Yang Guang's support to build a monastery on Mount Tiantai, which was completed with Yang's support. Yang, after ascending the throne, gave named it Guoqing Temple (国清寺), and it became the most important monastery affiliated with Tiantai in China. Scholars observed the dramatic decline of Tiantai in the early Tang and suspected it was caused by the school's close ties with the Sui court. This view has been challenged by Jinhua Chen, who argues that the "decline" began during the Sui -- just several years after Zhiyi's death, Tiantai had fallen out of imperial favor. Yet, as Chen's research shows, Guanding's disciples promoted their master's close connection to Emperor Yang in several fabricated documents. During the chaotic late Tang and Five Dynasties period, the kingdom of Wu Yue (907-978) in southeastern China, where Mount Tiantai is located, provided a relatively peaceful and supportive environment for Buddhism across different traditions. Consequently this region became a bastion of Tiantai until the 20th century when Tanxu spread Tiantai to Manchuria and Hong Kong. While the Tiantai patriarch Zhili of the early Song counted the emperor as patron, from the Yuan to Qing dynasty, Tiantai did not seem to command a close relationship with the court. In the Ming, for

example, its main supporters were scholar-officials from the region of Wu Yue, whose wealth and positions in the bureaucracy were often precarious.

Reference: Benjamin Brose. *Patrons and Patriarchs*. University of Hawaii Press. isbn: 9780824857240.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but neither always nor exclusively. Emperor Wen (r. 581 -604) of the Sui Dynasty persisted in his patronage of Zhiyi and his group, partly in an effort to placate the southern elite. But just several years after Zhiyi's death, Tiantai was out of the imperial favor, though it may have still been financially supported by them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but neither always nor exclusively. Important Tiantai monasteries, most of which are located in the southeast near the Lower Yangtze delta, became increasingly independent from the court in late imperial times (16-19th centuries).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: Tiantai Patriarchs, who were only recognized as patriarchs after they died, were never heads of the polity. There has never been a living "head" of Tiantai Buddhism other than several highly reputable and influential Tiantai monks.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Before the time of Zhiyi and Guanding, monks were invited to head monasteries irrespective of their theoretical orientation. But after the late Northern and Southern Dynasties (317-589), the practice of donating estates or tax bases to monasteries and/or specific teachers of particular doctrines or texts became more popular, especially in the Sui (Penkower, 1997, p.1331). For example, in a decree dated the sixth day of the second month in T'ai-Chien 9 (577), Emperor Xuan of the Chen dynasty commanded that a portion of the taxes derived from Shifeng County (縣) be applied to the support of Zhiyi and his monastic community, and also that two households of that county be excused from their other civic duties in order to provide "firewood and water" to that community (Hurvitz, 137). This practice may have stimulated interest in creating lineage accounts to protect temple property, as we find Guanding doing (Penkower, 1997, 1331).

Reference: Leon Hurvitz. *Chih-I (538-599): An Introduction to the Life and Ideas of a Chinese Buddhist Monk*. Bruxelles: Inst. Belge des Hautes Etudes Chinoises.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is not a congregational religion group so it is impossible to count or estimate.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: Most lay Buddhists in China do not exclusively identify themselves with a particular school such as Tiantai or Chan, and many who believe in and practice Buddhism also believe in and adhere to Daoist and Confucian teachings at the same time. Not all Buddhist monastics have an exclusive affiliation with a certain school, either. Tiantai, just like Chan, is a one of the schools that belong to Chinese Buddhism, but the boundaries are very fuzzy except for a small group of monastics who strongly attach themselves to the Tiantai tradition and lineage, whereas Tiantai philosophy has long been influential and Tiantai rituals are practiced widely.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There is a hierarchy, but it is very different from the kind seen in the Catholic Church. The hierarchy among Chinese Buddhist monastics resembles that in a traditional family. Monks of a younger generation are not supposed to challenge monks of an older generation, and nuns not to challenge monks. But this consensus is loose. While among monks of the same generation, the senior ones may receive more respect than the junior ones, their master may prefer those with spiritual or academic talents and make them leaders of their peers.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural powers or qualities are not necessary for a leader. But there are legends depicting the supernatural power of some leaders, such as Zhiyi's taming of a dragon.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: The leadership is not gained by birth.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: The historical Buddha is considered infallible. Narratives of eminent monks within their tradition or faction portrait them only positively and do not discuss the controversial or negative sides.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: For the Tiantai School, the supreme and at the same time accessible scripture in this system is the Lotus Sutra. Thus, it is also called the Lotus [Sutra] School (法華宗). Tiantai is also well known for its classification of the entire Buddhist Canon into a system called "Five Periods and Eight Teachings" 五時八教 (Wushi bajiao). This system was created to explain the discrepancies between sutras, based on the idea that the Buddha preached them at different points during his pedagogical career to audiences with different spiritual capacities. The five periods correspond to what is believed to be the five major chronological periods of the Buddha's teaching career: (1) Huayan (Avatamsaka Sutra) Period. The Huayan (Avatamsaka) Sutra is the initial account of his awakening that the Buddha taught immediately after his enlightenment. (2) Ahan (Āgama) or Deer Park Period. This is when the Buddha accommodated those disciples who were confounded during the first period, by teaching his insights in their most elementary, "Hīnayāna" form. (3) Fangdeng (Vaipulya) Period. The aspiration for Mahāyāna was introduced and the "Hīnayāna" teachings of the second period were superseded; this includes various sūtras that explicitly compare Mahāyāna favourably to Hīnayāna. (4) Bore (Prajñāpāramitā) Period. The Buddha began to remove the boundaries separating Mahāyāna and "Hīnayāna" by leading his audience from the presumption that there were two separate vehicles to instead a common realization of emptiness. (5) Fahua Niepan (Lotus and Nirvāna) Period. The

teachings associated with this period, recorded in the Lotus Sutra and the Mahāparinirvāṇa Sūtra, are described as the “consummate” or “perfect” teachings because they espouse the idea of “one vehicle,” which Tiantai claimed was the truest form of the Buddha’s original intention. “Eight Teachings” refer to the way in which the entirety of the Buddhist canon and its teachings can be divided into two groups of four teachings each. Group I: “The four modes of transformative teachings”(huafa sijiao 化法四教), which classifies Buddhism into four categories based on content: (1) Zangjiao 藏教: The “tripitaka teachings,” which refer to the basic teachings foundational to the “Hīnayāna” schools, such as the notions of impermanence, suffering, and no-self, and the imperative of attaining Nirvana; (2) Tongjiao 通教: The “joint” or “common teachings,” a basic strand of Mahāyāna teaching that shares many of the preceding doctrinal themes jointly with the “hīnayāna teachings,” the main difference being that it additionally embraces the bodhisattva aspiration of helping others; (3) Biejiao 別教: The “distinct” or “separate teachings,” so named because, unlike the previous category, this strand of Mahāyāna includes notions exclusive to that tradition and not shared with the “Hīnayāna”; (4) Yuanjiao 圓教, the “consummate” or “perfect teaching,” which refers to the Lotus Sutra. Group II: The modes of exposition or conversion (huayi sijiao 化儀四教), which include the following divisions based on pedagogical style: (1) Dunjiao 頓教: The “sudden teachings” or a direct pedagogical style, epitomized by the Avatamsaka Sutra. (2) Jianjiao 漸教: The “gradual teachings,” the sequential, step-by-step approaches and pedagogical styles, represented by the āgamas, the prajñāpāramitā sūtras, and the vaipulya sūtras. (3) Budingjiao 不定教: The “indefinite teachings,” the teachings that the Buddha gave without differentiation to everyone, but which people of different spiritual maturity may understand immediately or gradually, fully or in part. (4) Mimijiao 秘密教: The “hidden teachings” that the Buddha put in his sermons mainly targeting a different audience. For example, Mahāyāna messages “hidden” in some Āgama texts belong to this category because the “Hīnayāna” audience does not even know they exist. Besides the Lotus Sutra, the most fundamental texts for the school are referred to as the “three great texts of Tiantai” or “three great texts of the Lotus,” which are three works by Zhiyi: The Great Cessation and Contemplation (T.1911, 摩訶止觀, which has been fully translated into English), Profound Meaning of the Lotus Sutra (T.1716, 法華玄義), and Words and Phrases of the Lotus Sutra (T.1718, 法華文句). Penkower argued that many features people use to define Tiantai tradition, such as the supremacy of the Lotus Sutra, Three Great Texts by Zhiyi as its foundation, and the “five periods and eight teachings” taxonomy, were in fact substantially shaped by Zhanran 湛然(711-782). Zhanran insisted that true transmission be grounded in scriptural authority. He promoted the status of the Lotus Sutra to quintessential scriptural authority not only for Tiantai teachings but also for meditative practices, as found in the Mohe zhiguan. He shifted the focus away from dependence upon an Indian exegetical text (Da zhidu lun 大智度論) to a scripture work (Lotus) with an authoritative Chinese commentator (that is, Zhiyi), which is an assimilative strategy shared by most Tang traditions (Penkower 1997, 1318). Some Chinese apocryphal scriptures are also significant for Tiantai philosophy and practices. Zhiyi cited Yingluo jing and Renwang jing as the principal sources for his “three truths” theory (Donner and Stevenson, 8).

Reference: Neal Donner , Daniel Stevenson. The Great Calming and Contemplation: A Study and Annotated Translation of the First Chapter of Chih-i's Mo-ho Chih-kuan. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press.

Reference: Linda Penkower undefined. Making and Remaking Tradition: Chan-Jan’s Strategies toward a Tang T'ien-t'ai Agenda. (Tendai daishi no), Tendai daishi no kenkyuu 天台大師研究: 天台大師千四百年御遠忌記念 (A Study of Great Master Tiantai). Tokyo: Tendai gakkai.

Reference: Robert E. Buswell (Jr.), Donald S. Lopez (Jr.), Juhn Ahn. The Princeton Dictionary of Buddhism. isbn: 9780190681159.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 538 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Zhiyi's disciple Guanding in his biography of Zhiyi claimed that Zhiyi's master Huisi and Zhiyi had listened to the Buddha preach the Lotus Sutra in a past life (Penkower 2000, 261 ff).

Reference: Linda Penkower undefined. In the Beginning ... Guanding 灌顶 (561-632) and the Creation of Early Tiantai. *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies*, 23(2)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture that Tiantai hold as the highest, the Lotus Sutra, is believed to have been preached by the Buddha. According to the Lotus Sutra itself (Chapter 12 "Devadatta" in Kumarajiva's version), the Buddha learned this sutra in a previous life, when he was a devoted Buddhist king, from a sage, whom he would serve diligently for one thousand years and who was reborn in this current life as his cousin Devadatta. This narrative regarding the origin of the Lotus Sutra was most likely intended to explain why Devadatta, as recorded in earlier Buddhist literature, always tried to harm the Buddha and sometime even succeeded in doing so, given that the Buddha is supposed to be omnipotent and free of bad karma as many Mahayana Buddhists tend to believe. This narrative shows that the Buddha had been in Devadatta's debt for the Lotus Sutra. Zhiyi's works also became fundamental for Tiantai, and in the same process, miraculous abilities were added to Zhiyi's biography so that he was considered by the tradition as a divine or semi-divine human being (Shinohara 1992).

Reference: Koichi Shinohara. Guanding's Biography of Zhiyi, the Fourth Patriarch of the Tiantai Tradition. (Phyllis Granola, Koichi Shinohara), *Speaking of Monks: Religious Biography in India and China*. United Kingdom: Mosaic Press.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: An exception may be Gong Zizhen (1792-1841), a famous poet, political thinker, and self-identified Tiantai Buddhist, who claimed in 1837 that "1444 years after the Lotus Sutra was introduced to China ... I, Gong Zizhen, decide to be the first person to correct it." He pointed to several chapters and passages as fabricated and re-organized the sequence of some of the remaining chapters, based on the narrative inconsistencies he detected and his own ethical standard.

Reference: Lang Chen. *Repressed Modern Buddhism? On Gong Zizhen (1792 - 1841)'s Buddhist Thoughts and Praxis*. Presented at AAR annual meeting 2020,

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: No currently. But there was a well-known doctrinal dispute within Tiantai in the 10th century. After the death of Zhanran, especially after the Huichang persecution (842-846), Tiantai found itself in crisis, while Chan demonstrated an outstanding capacity for synthesizing ideas from other Buddhist schools. Qingliang Chengguan (738-839), the fourth Huayan patriarch, had studied under Zhanran and incorporated in his work elements of both Chan and Tiantai, including the notion of inherent evil in the Buddha nature. Yet Chengguan's student Guifeng Zongmi (780-841) eliminated the Tiantai influence but absorbed ideas from Chan and Huayan. Deshao (881-972), renowned in his time as a reviver of Tiantai, was closely associated with the Fayen branch of Chan, and his student Yongming Yanshou (954-974), influenced by Zongmi, attempted to unify Tiantai, Huayan, and Yogacara teachings under a form of Chan theorizing the "one pure formless mind." Against this background, Tiantai ideas and practices "appeared quaint and cumbersome." Zongmi's version of Chan doctrine became the most common target of Tiantai polemics. Those Tiantai adherents who admitted the superiority of these new elements (the one pure mind, the original absence of defilement, etc.) by claiming that these were originally Tiantai doctrines were later labeled as "shanwai" (outside [Tiantai] mountain) heterodox. Those holding that the Tiantai views on the Buddha nature etc. were different from and superior to the Zongmi/Chan view became the "shanjia" (home mountain masters) orthodox. Zhili classified Chan under the "special teaching" (biejiao), only rejecting the claim that Chan surpasses Tiantai's perfect, "round" teaching (yuanjiao). Zyporyn deems the real stakes of the doctrinal debates between Shanjia and Shanwai, between Tiantai and Chan (or other schools) were materialist and practical: to secure sponsorship and power (Zyporyn 1994, 28).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Works by Zhiyi have been studied by all scholarly monks across the Buddhist tradition, though they, as well as other works by important Tiantai patriarchs and eminent monks, may be further stressed in monasteries/Buddhist academies related to Tiantai. Texts have always been important for Tiantai, and people of this tradition were often proud of their texts for not being esoteric, but able to speak for themselves.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Some Chinese religious architecture, such as pagodas, may fit into the definition provided but some do not. For example, the architecture of even very important temples is still very practical; their large size was made to host many monastics. Some monuments could be very small, such as the stone shrine dedicated to Zhiyi's taming of demons (picture attached in a question below).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: There are monasteries that have been permanently or temporarily associated with Tiantai. For example, Guoqing Monastery and Gaoming Monastery on Mt. Tiantai (Zhejiang Province), Guanzong Monastery in Ningbo (Zhejiang Province), and Lengyan Monastery in Yingkou (Liaoning Province).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Altars:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the pagoda on Mount Tiantai dedicated to the Zhiyi's taming of demons.

Reference: Daijō Tokiwa, Tadashi Sekino. *Wanqing minguo shiqi Zhongguo mingsheng guji tuji* 晚清民國時期中國名勝古跡圖集. Beijing: China Pictorial Press. isbn: 9787514613919 7514613919. p.26

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

Notes: Iconography of Tiantai patriarchs is not as prevalent in China as that of Guanyin, Amitabha, or Maitreya. But Gong Zizhen, who identified himself as a Tiantai Buddhist, wrote that he had put a sandalwood statue of Zhiyi in his home in 1839 (Chen, 2020). Another scholar-official, Tu Long, in the early 17th century described a "Tiantai ancestral courtyard" 天台祖庭 newly built in Gaoming Monastery on Mt. Tiantai, where the images (either statues or paintings) of the Buddha, Bodhisattvas, the twenty-nine Tiantai Patriarchs, and a Ming Tiantai master (Baisong) were displayed (Chen 2019). Currently, images of the patriarchs, which seem to have been created in recent decades, are displayed in the same building where Zhiyi's stupa is housed (see example images below).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Tu Long in the early 17th century described a "Tiantai ancestral courtyard" 天台祖庭 newly built under the advocacy of Chuandeng as follows: "The image of Shakyamuni is set in the middle. The attendant on his east is Mañjuśrī and on his west is Maitreya. This is different from the layout in other monasteries because this one is based on the Lotus Sūtra that the

Tiantai School regards as its root: At the outset of this sūtra, when the Tathāgata entered meditation, Maitreya asked Mañjuśrī to explain the meaning of it ...(Tu Long, "Xinjian Tiantai zuting ji 新建天台祖庭記," Tiantaishan fangwaizhi, CBETA, GA90, no. 89, p. 814, a9 ff)" Whether all Tiantai monasteries followed or still follow this iconography needs to be investigated.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - No
- ↳ Humans:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Mount Tiantai, especially Guoqing Monastery 国清寺, has been considered most significant, if not sacred, for the Tiantai tradition. Guoqing Monastery was conceived by Zhiyi shortly before he died. In

his last letter to his main patron Prince Yang Guang, he requested that the Prince build it after he died. With the sponsorship of Yang Guang, it was completed in 601, one year after Yang became the Crown Prince, and in 605 it was renamed Guoqing by Yang Guang who had just ascended the throne. Consequently, Zhiyi's request to Yang Guang in his will was interpreted as "an example of his miraculous foresight" (Shinohara, 1992, 111). The Korean prince/monk Uich'on 義天 (1055-1101) travelled to China in 1085 with the intention of studying Huayan and became interested in Tiantai while he was in China. Returning to Korea in 1086, he lamented the dominance of Son (Chan) and, supported by his royal family members, he made the new Cheontae (Ch. Tiantai) school rise to power. He used travelers and monks to bring to Korea thousands of scrolls of texts in both traditions. In 1097, Kukch'ong Temple (Ch. Guoqing si) was built in Korea for Uich'on, who is considered the first patriarch of Ch'ont'ae in Korea. From the late 11th century on, the Cheontae became a significant force in Korean Buddhism (Brose, 2006, 41).

Reference: Ben Brose. Crossing Thousands of Li of Waves: The Return of China's lost Tiantai texts. *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies*, 29(1)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: As far as I know, there is no regular pilgrimage dedicated to the Tiantai tradition. However, Tiantai was closely related to the Guanyin pilgrimage in Hangzhou. During the Five Dynasties and Northern Song period the Upper Tianzhu Monastery 上天竺寺 in Hangzhou, famed for its numinously potent statue of Guanyin, became an increasingly powerful cultic and pilgrimage site. In the Northern Song, the Hangzhou prefect Shen Gou converted this monastery from Chan to Tiantai, initiating a continuous stream of Tiantai abbots that lasted through the Yuan and the Ming. Stevenson reasoned that the Tiantai rituals such as the Invocation of Guanyin Repentance and the Great Compassion Repentance probably became the main liturgies used in ceremonies at the Upper Tianzhu Monastery (Stevenson 1999, 359). Nowadays pilgrims still visit that monastery, though it is not clear if it is affiliated with Tiantai.

Reference: Daniel Stevenson B.. *Protocols of Power: Tz'u-yün Tsun-shih (964-1032) and T'ien-t'ai Lay Buddhist Ritual in the Sung.* (Peter Gregory N. , Daniel Getz A.), *Buddhism in the Sung*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Notes: As the boundary of Tiantai as a religious group is not as clear as it is for congregational religious groups, the term "rare" or "common" could be misleading in this context. Pilgrims are mostly laities, and laities usually do not identify themselves with Tiantai or any other Buddhist school.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Here I take "adherents" to refer to eminent monks, not ordinary monks or lay supporters. The body of its founder Zhiyi was said to be preserved in his stupa. Relics are supposed to be found after an eminent monk is cremated and a stupa is built to contain the ashes and relics. But these practices are shared by all Buddhist schools, and thus may not be considered "special."

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ **Mummification:**

– Yes

Notes: It is said that Zhiyi's stupa contains his mummy. This practice or myth was usually reserved for the founder or the most important figure of a Buddhist school.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ **Interment:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ **Cannibalism:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ **Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ **Feeding to animals:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ **Secondary burial:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ **Re-treatment of corpse:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Burials for Tiantai monastics should follow the generic protocol of Chinese Buddhist burials for monastics.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: stupa

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddha can be considered such a "high god," but the Buddha is not necessarily singular. There is a multitude of buddhas who are at the same level of "importance." But they can be considered manifestations of the Dharmakaya of the Buddha.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

Notes: The Buddha can be considered such a "high god," but the Buddha is not necessarily singular. There is a multitude of buddhas who are at the same level of "importance." But they can be considered manifestations of the Dharmakaya of the Buddha. Dharmakaya -- the Dharma Body -- is usually not imagined anthropomorphically in Tiantai tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Some emperors in China, most remarkably Empress Wu, and their supporters, tried to make this claim. But it is not directly related to Tiantai.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: But the Tiantai doctrine of "nature" (xing 性) contends that the nature of any being, including the Buddha, includes both good and evil. The Buddha is able to do both the good and evil deeds, but if the Buddha does something that appears evil, he does it as a means to achieve a good end.

Reference: Brook Ziporyn undefined. *Evil And/or/as the Good Omnicentrism, Intersubjectivity, and Value Paradox in Tiantai Buddhist Thought*. Cambridge MA:

Harvard University Asia Center. isbn: 9781684170340.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. According to Buddhism, human behaviours and the results of their behaviours are affected by their previous karma (in this life and in previous lives), but not completely determined by it.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The Buddhas also know one's previous lives.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: According to Buddhism, one's own karma (deeds/acts) brings rewards or punishments. But worshipping the Buddha, considered a very good karma, may bring rewards or reduce punishment due. For those less informed about Buddhist doctrines, it is the Buddha who punishes and rewards.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: According to Buddhism, one's own karma (deeds/acts) brings rewards or punishments. But worshipping the Buddha, considered a very good karma, may bring rewards or reduce punishment due.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Tiantai doctrine of nature, the buddhas have the potential to exhibit negative emotion and use it as a skillful means.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: The Sakyamuni Buddha, according to many versions of his biography, possessed hunger, but this was often interpreted in the Mahayana and Chinese Buddhism as a skillful means the Buddha manifested to make connections to ordinary people and to teach the lesson of suffering and impermanence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god exhibits not only hunger, but also illness, injuries and other forms of suffering, according to Mahayana interpretation, to teach humans about impermanence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: I have not seen this in Tiantai-related texts. But since trance possession is common in Chinese religion, it would not be surprising for some to claim to have been possessed by the Buddha.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: A famous example is that Ouyi Zhixu 藕益智旭 (1599-1655) consulted the Buddha through divination about which Buddhist school he should specialize in. With the result being Tiantai, Ouyi became an eminent monk in Tiantai teachings and was posthumously recognized as a Tiantai patriarch.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: in meditation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: The most well-known previously human spirit in the Tiantai tradition may be Guan Yu 關羽 (? - 219/220). According to an inscription dated to 802, the oldest source that connects the worship of Guan Yu with the Yuquan monastery, the spirit of Guan Yu appeared before Zhiyi and helped him build the Monastery. The monastery is located where Guan Yu had been executed in late 219 or early 220, where the worship of Guan Yu started. Compared with Guanding's biography of Zhiyi, in which the divine force Zhiyi faced was a local dragon, Ter Haar contends that Guan Yu's connection to Tiantai did not appear until around 800.

Reference: Barend J. ter Haar. Guan Yu. Oxford University Press. isbn: 9780192525420.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on the nature of the particular human spirit and thus cannot be generalised.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on the nature of the particular human spirit and thus cannot be generalised.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on the nature of the particular human spirit and thus cannot be generalised.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes

Notes: Ancestor worship in China is based on this belief. Tiantai followers sometimes prayed to famous Tiantai patriarchs like Zhiyi to aid in their spiritual achievements.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: The ghost of a murdered person may take revenge on their murderer, but both the murder and the revenge can also be interpreted as karmic retribution. Whether it is direct or indirect depends on the interpretation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: In 1627 Jin Shengtian 金聖歎 (1610-1661) claimed that the spirit of a disciple of Zhiyi began to speak through him by spirit writing. Around 1636, the spirit commanded Jin's friend Qian Qianyi 錢謙益 (1582-1664) to write an essay approving the credibility of spirit writing and Tiantai teaching, and it also told him that he was the reincarnation of the great monk Huiyuan 慧遠 (334-416) of Mt. Lu. Qian wrote this essay together with ten poems.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Notes: It depends on the nature of this non-human supernatural beings. There are local deities or local manifestations of the Guanyin bodhisattva, the legends of whom were only popular regionally. But Guanyin's popularity transcended the sample regions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Yes and no. According to Buddhism, human behaviors and the results of those behaviors are affected by their previous karma (in this life and in previous lives), but not completely determined by it.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: knowledge about one's previous lives.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: One's own karma (deeds/acts) brings reward or punishment. But worshipping bodhisattvas, considered a good karmic act, will bring rewards or reduce the punishment due.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: One's own karma (deeds/acts) brings reward or punishment. But worshipping bodhisattvas, considered a good karmic act, will bring rewards or reduce the punishment due.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Based on Buddhist cosmology, which considers the universe to consist of six realms, Tiantai often divides the universe further into ten realms: those of hell-beings, hungry ghosts, animals, asuras, humans, gods, śrāvakas, pratyekabuddhas, bodhisattvas, and buddhas, many of which can be seen as "supernatural."

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: As in Buddhism generally, humans' behavior and thought are monitored by the idea of karma, though people who do not know much about Buddhist doctrines may consider buddhas and bodhisattvas to be like Chinese deities who surveil them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: As in Buddhism in general, bad karma naturally causes retribution, though people who do not know much about Buddhist doctrines may consider buddhas and bodhisattvas to be like Chinese deities who mete out punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: As in Buddhism generally, good karma naturally causes rewards, though people who do not know much about Buddhist doctrines may consider buddhas and bodhisattvas to be like Chinese deities who bestow rewards.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Tiantai follows the Madhyamaka philosophy in Indian Buddhism that distinguishes conventional truth (or provisional truth) and ultimate truth (or the truth of emptiness). The ultimate truth refers to the ultimate empty essence of all existence and transcends the distinction between good and evil. The conventional truth enjoins people not to neglect or deny the existence of beings and the moral laws that need to be followed. According to Tiantai, one is supposed to balance between the two truths, without neglecting either, to achieve the Truth of the Mean. Therefore, philosophically, instead of the distinction between convention and morality, the distinction in Tiantai Buddhism is between the moral and the supra-moral. But this does not mean that Tiantai monks and supporters did not sometimes go against convention. For example, Zunshi (964 -1032) campaigned against meat and wine sacrifice (Stevenson 1999, 350).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Among Buddhist practitioners, celibacy is required for monks and nuns, but not for the laity. In this and the following questions, it is worth noting that the word "membership" can be misleading when used to discuss Chinese Buddhism. Since Chinese Buddhism is not congregational, its membership and identification with a particular school such as Tiantai is usually not exclusive and thus does not play an important role. With the exception of some elite monks engaged in debates regarding doctrines, the monastics usually do not cling to a "Tiantai identity," never mind ordinary laity. Therefore, my answers to this and most of the following questions are not limited to Tiantai but can be applied to Chinese Buddhists in general.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not required regularly for the laity; monks and nuns may follow the general Buddhist monastic precepts to refrain from eating after lunch time. Fasting is also required for participants in some rituals.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Among all practitioners of Chinese Buddhism, monastics are not supposed to consume alcohol, meat, the “five forbidden pungent roots” including leeks, scallions, garlic, onions, and chives. Forgoing these foods is not required for the laity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Burning one's head at ordination was required for Buddhist monastics in China during the late imperial time.

Reference: James Benn. Where Text Meets Flesh: Burning the Body as an Apocryphal Practice in Chinese Buddhism. *History of Religions*, 37(4)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Monastics and lay supporters of the Tiantai tradition are supposed to accept the same ethical precepts all Chinese Buddhists must adhere to. All Buddhists in China are supposed to accept five basic ethical precepts (Skt. pañca-sīla): not killing, not stealing, no debauchery, no false speech, and no consumption of alcohol (though this final precept is often ignored by lay Buddhists). In addition, the monastics are required to follow monastic rules. The laity and monastics can also take on "bodhisattva precepts." Zhiyi's *Pusajie yishu* 菩薩戒義疏 (Commentary on Bodhisattva Precepts) profoundly influenced the tradition of bodhisattva precepts in China, rendering the Brahmā's Net precepts more popular than the Yogācāra precepts and thus the mainstream practice in China (Lin 2021). Several other Tiantai or Tiantai-related monks such as Zhili 知禮 (960-1028), Zunshi 遵式 (964-1032), and Yuanzhao 元照 (1048-1116) produced ritual manuals for transmitting bodhisattva precepts (Getz 2005).

Reference: Pei-ying Lin. Introduction: Bendable Buddhist Law. *The Eastern Buddhist*, 49(1)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Ordination rituals are required for becoming a monastic "member" of Chinese Buddhism. Various rituals are part of the monastic life and each monastic is supposed to participate in them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: The ordination ritual entails some synchronic practices.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Head shaving is the most salient marker for Chinese Buddhist monastics, and applies to all Buddhist monastics in China. There is no particular marker for Tiantai practitioners.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: Since the seventeenth century, it was very common for Buddhist monks and nuns to have their scalps or arms burned by cones of moxa at ordination. This is rarely practised nowadays. In mainland China it was officially renounced in the early 1980s (Benn 1998).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: As for all practitioners of Chinese Buddhism, the monastics are not supposed to consume alcohol, meat, “five forbidden pungent roots” including leeks, scallions, garlic, onions, and chives. Forgoing these foods is not required for the laity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Monastics are supposed to shave their heads.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist monastics wear particular robes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: Many Buddhists carry rosary-like "recitation beads" with them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Lineage plays a significant role in Tiantai tradition as in other Chinese Buddhist schools such as Chan. As in other schools, the lineage is made of a line of eminent monks (all male), who are called patriarchs (zu 祖). Disciples are called "Dharma sons" (法子), and disciple's disciples are called "Dharma grandsons" (法孫).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

Notes: It is mainly used to describe the teacher-disciple relationship.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not clear in the question how uncommon is considered uncommon. It seems to me very difficult to measure.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Tiantai "belongs to" a state in the sense that it is regulated by each state where it is located. Chinese Tiantai is transnational and can be found in Hong Kong (even before it returned to China in 1997), Taiwan, Canada, Malaysia, and so forth.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: What the word "adherent" refers to in this and the following questions is not clear to me, just as the word "membership" in some other questions. In China even the identity of being a Buddhist is very fluid and not exclusive, not to mention the identity of belonging to a certain Buddhist school.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear what "formal" and "adherents" refer to in this question. Since the early twentieth century, there have been Buddhist academies for the monastics, as well as k-12 schools, founded by Tiantai monks or nuns or affiliated with Tiantai monasteries to various degrees, but most of them did not and do not serve the Tiantai "adherents" only but are open to people of all backgrounds. Below are the most influential ones. In 1913, Ven. Dixian 諦閑 (1858-1932), the abbot of the Guanzong Monastery, a historic Tiantai monastery, set up the Guanzong Study Society (Guanzong yanjiu she 觀宗研究社) within the monastery, which was later renamed the Guanzong School (Guanzong Xueshe 觀宗學社) and then Dharma Propagation Study Society (Hongfa yanjiushe 弘法研究社). The admission was expanded from resident monks at the Guanzong Monastery to include a small number of monks from outside. The curriculum focused primarily on Tiantai doctrine and its pedagogy seemed rather traditional compared with some of its contemporary Buddhist academies that followed a more westernized approach. The academy Dixian founded produced a generation of graduates who, armed with a specialized training in Tiantai doctrines, went on to establish or teach at other monastic schools across the country. Tanxu 倓虛 (1875-1962), one of the most prominent graduates and recognized as the Tiantai Dharma Heir of the forty-fourth generation, succeeded in establishing thirteen Buddhist academies in northern China, and after 1948, in Hong Kong. Xiaoyun 曉雲 (1912-2004), a nun artist and tonsure disciple of Tanxu in Hong Kong, founded the first Buddhist university (Huafan University 華梵大

學) in Taiwan in 1990, which is open to both monastics and the laity. Some other disciples of Tanxu spread the Dharma to Canada and the United States. In addition to education for monastics and higher education, there are several elementary schools in Hong Kong affiliated with Tiantai, though they are open to children of all backgrounds.

Reference: Billy 家宙 Tang鄧. History of Buddhism in Hong Kong 香港佛教史. Hong Kong: 中華書局.

Reference: Rongdao Lai undefined. Tiantai Transnationalism: Mobility, Identity, and Lineage Networks in Modern Chinese Buddhism. (Philip Clart, Adam Jones undefined, Ed.), Transnational Religious Spaces: Religious Organizations and Interactions in Africa, East Asia, and Beyond. Berlin/Boston: De Gruyter. isbn: 978-3-11-068995-2.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear if there is a "formal bureaucracy" within Tiantai, though it certainly exists in any monastery, whether or not it is related to Tiantai.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: This only applies to the monastics, referring to ostracism from the monastic community.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Historically yes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: It is the monastic precepts that all Buddhist monastics in China follow. I do not think there is any set of precepts only applicable to the Tiantai monasteries, as far as I know.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It is possible. Some of its lay supporters may work for the military and when the country was mobilized for war, monks may have been drafted.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Notes: a formal calendar distinctively Tiantai or not?

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: I wonder what "formal calendar" refers to.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Traditionally Buddhist monasteries in China relied on the rent of the lands they owned.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2021 CE

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